

GINAMO workshop on genetic diversity indicators in Italy

Bologna, 18 March 2025

REPORT

This research was funded by Biodiversa+, the European Biodiversity Partnership, in the context of the GINAMO project under the 2022-2023 BiodivMon joint call. It was co-funded by the European Commission (GA No. 101052342) The Research Council of Norway, The Belgian Science Policy, L'Agence nationale de la recherche, Ministero dell'Università, Naturvårdsverket, Rymdstyrelsen, Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft and Innovation Fund Denmark

The workshop was financially supported by: University of Bologna

ALMA MATER STUDIORUM
UNIVERSITÀ DI BOLOGNA

Acknowledgements	3
GINAMO Genetic Indicators for Nature Monitoring	4
Main objectives	4
Main activities	4
Workshop process	5
Participants	6
Workshop evaluation	6
Workshop results	6
Workshop outcomes	6
Where in the workflow stakeholder's institutions might contribute	7
Summary of current situation in Italy	8
Challenges	9
Species list to monitor and report on	9
Data is collected, structured and stored and calculating the indicators	10
The report to the CBD is written and submitted	10
Next steps	11
Reference materials	12
APPENDIX I: Workshop Agenda	13
APPENDIX II: institutions represented	13
APPENDIX III: IUCN SSC CPSG	16

Acknowledgements

Authors: Julia Geue (University of Freiburg), Christina Ritzl Vejlgard (Copenhagen Zoo), Kristin Leus (Copenhagen Zoo), Daniele Battilani (CRI - Fondazione E. Mach), Cristiano Vernesi (CRI - Fondazione E. Mach), Christina Hvilsom (Copenhagen Zoo)

Organising team: Cristiano Vernesi (GINAMO, CRI - Fondazione E. Mach), Vittorio De Cristofaro (CBD National Focal Point for Italy Officer of the Ministry of Environment and Energy Security), Lorenzo Ciccarese (Institute for Protection and Research on Environment - ISPRA), Kristin Leus (Copenhagen Zoo, IUCN SSC CPSG), Christina Ritzl Vejlgard (Copenhagen Zoo, IUCN SSC CPSG)

Workshop design and facilitation: Kristin Leus (Copenhagen Zoo, IUCN SSC CPSG), Christina Ritzl Vejlgard (Copenhagen Zoo, IUCN SSC CPSG), Julia Geue (University of Freiburg)

Workshop host: University of Bologna

Note taking: Daniele Battilani (CRI - Fondazione E. Mach), Julia Geue (University of Freiburg)

Workshop evaluation by GINAMO: Carina Lundmark (Luleå University of Technology), Eva Theunissen (Royal Zoological Society of Antwerp), Kristin Leus (Copenhagen Zoo), Christina Ritzl Vejlgard (Copenhagen Zoo), Julia Geue (University of Freiburg)

Introductory presentations: Kristin Leus (GINAMO, Copenhagen Zoo, IUCN SSC CPSG), Cristiano Vernesi (GINAMO, CRI - Fondazione E. Mach)

Suggested citation: Geue, J. C., Vejlgard, C. R., Leus, K., Battilani, D., Vernesi, C., & Hvilsom, C. (2025). *GINAMO workshop on genetic diversity indicators in Italy* (project report). GINAMO: Genetic Indicators for Nature Monitoring. DOI:<https://zenodo.org/records/17017695>

GINAMO Genetic Indicators for Nature Monitoring

Genetic diversity is the foundation of biodiversity and essential for the long-term survival, adaptation, and resilience of populations, species, and entire ecosystems. While genetic diversity has long been neglected in biodiversity policy and management, the current Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD)

Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework (GBF) includes a strong goal and target for genetic diversity conservation and also monitoring, including with indicators and for wild species. Tools and indicators to assess and monitor genetic diversity are available but are rarely applied due to the gap in knowledge transfer between conservation science and application. GINAMO is a project of Biodiversa+, The European Biodiversity Partnership, which assesses and delivers science-based and co-designed best practices and guidelines for the use of genetic diversity indicators. This will enable the routine integration of genetic criteria and indicators into biodiversity monitoring and assessments, from policy at regional, national, and EU levels, to global conventions and obligations. A key component of GINAMO is the use of facilitated group decision-making processes to partner and co-decide from the outset with the stakeholder community. This ensures that all resources produced meet their concerns, reporting duties, and monitoring needs, and that guidelines and work flows are more likely to be adopted. Easy-to-apply, standardised and automated workflows will be co-created for assessing genetic indicators to meet national reporting obligations and to incorporate genetic diversity knowledge into nature management plans.

Main objectives

GINAMO uses existing open access genetic and non-genetic data (including Earth observation data) to best determine accurate estimates of the two genetic diversity indicators of the GBF: 1) the proportion of populations within species with an effective population size (N_e) greater than 500 ($N_e > 500$ hereafter), and 2) the proportion of populations maintained within species. To maximise the implementation and reporting of these indicators, GINAMO designs, facilitates, and scientifically evaluates co-creation processes between scientists and country stakeholders in France, Norway, Belgium, Sweden and Italy. These processes aim to collaboratively develop workflows that are scientifically sound, appropriate, compliant with policy and easy-to-implement for nature management.

Main activities

GINAMO focuses on generating best practices for assessing effective population size and evaluating genetic indicators from both DNA-based data and non-DNA (proxy) data from multiple sources. Additionally, GINAMO evaluates how satellite Earth observation data can be used to generate proxies to monitor genetic diversity. Workflows for existing and newly generated information will be standardised to provide easily accessible tools for researchers, nature managers and policy makers. GINAMO activities follow a co-creation approach under professional guidance by the European Regional Resource Center of the IUCN SSC [Conservation Planning Specialist Group](#) and with scientific evaluation by social scientists, so that methods and products are produced together by policy makers, nature managers, and scientists.

Workshop process

The workshops organised by GINAMO in collaboration with local country stakeholders serve to create input to the best practice guidelines that will be produced. In order to make these as user friendly and as relevant as possible, it is important to understand the realities in which various stakeholders operate, and to understand the challenges they experience from their perspective. The challenges identified during the workshops will inform the work of the various work packages within GINAMO, when developing the science and methods behind the use of genetic indicators.

IUCN SSC CPSG Europe designed and facilitated the country workshop processes, in line with CPSG's Principles and Steps (Appendix III), and informed by preparatory meetings with a country organising group composed of GINAMO scientists from the country and selected country stakeholders with a central role in monitoring and reporting on biodiversity.

In preparation of the workshops, a generic workflow was developed (Fig 1), that outlines the main steps that need to be taken within a country in order to be able to report genetic indicators to the CBD. This workflow was used as the basis for the discussions during the workshop.

Fig 1. The generic workflow used as a base for the workshop.

The agenda for the workshop can be found in Appendix I. Following an introduction to the GINAMO project and the genetic indicators, as well as to the workshop process and generic workflow, the active part of the workshop started. Participants first identified where in the workflow they felt their institution could have a role to play. Next, the generic workflow was divided into three parts:

1. Selection of the species to monitor and report on.
2. Data collection, indicator calculation, and storing and structuring of metadata for future reporting cycles.
3. Preparing the relevant parts of the CBD report

For each of these three parts, the participants:

- A. Discussed their knowledge of the current situation in Italy
- B. Identified the challenges facing them as stakeholders, or the country as a whole, in order to end up with a fully functional, and repeatable workflow that can routinely and consistently produce genetic indicators for consecutive reporting cycles to CBD.

At the end of the workshop, the participants reviewed all the challenges and selected those for which they felt that developing solutions may benefit from collaboration with GINAMO (in other words, from co-creating solutions); versus those challenges that clearly need to be solved in-country.

Participants

The country organising group identified the stakeholders that would be invited to the workshop. A matrix was developed to help identify stakeholders that represented a wide variety of workflow steps, skills, roles and responsibilities, as well as geographical placement, when relevant. Not all the identified stakeholders were able to participate in the workshop, but they will all receive this report.

21 stakeholders representing various research institutes and NGOs participated. The workshop was held at the University of Bologna. The list of participants and a short description of the institutions represented can be found in Appendix II.

Workshop evaluation

GINAMO's social scientists will evaluate the entire co-creation process. In order to evaluate the country workshops, a survey was prepared and completed by all participants before and after the workshop. The only parts from that survey included in this report are any answers to the question: "List any stakeholders who could have made a valuable contribution but were not present at this workshop". The overall results from this evaluation will be shared at a later stage.

Workshop results

Workshop outcomes

1. An overview of the current situation in Italy with regards to: genetic monitoring and reporting, genetic and proxy data gathering and databases, already existing workflows, important stakeholder groups, scientific views regarding the use of the *Ne 500* headline indicator, etc.
2. A list of challenges facing the stakeholders and the country to have a fully functional workflow that is repeatable every 4 years as required of the CBD.
3. An agreed way forward for how we best approach each challenge – is it a possible GINAMO creation challenge or is this something that the country needs to solve?

This report collects the results from the workshop in Italy, and reflects the thoughts, assumptions and knowledge of the participants at the time of the workshop, but does not claim to give the full picture of the status and challenges with regards to the reporting of genetic indicators to the CBD in Italy. The aim of this report is to inform further work by GINAMO and hopefully it will also prove to be a useful first step towards further work and collaboration within Italy, to develop and implement a national workflow.

Where in the workflow stakeholder's institutions might contribute

The workshop participants identified where in the workflow they felt their institution might have a role to play. The results are in the table below. Please note that this does not constitute an exhaustive list of stakeholders required for each workflow step.

Data on species is generated	Data about species is stored	Species list to monitor and report on	Data is collected, structured and stored	Indicators are calculated and stored	The report to the CBD is written and submitted
Fondazione Edmund Mach - Centro Ricerca e Innovazione (FEM-CRI)	CNR IRET Porano	IZSLT (Istituto Zooprofilattico Sperimentale del Lazio e Toscana)	ISPRA (Animali, Fungi)	ISPRA (Animali, Fungi)	FEM - Ecologica Forestale
ERSAF Lombardia	CNR IBBR Firenze	FEM- genetic improvement		University of Torino (DISAFA)	
Centro BIODNA at Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore	University of Bologna	CNR IRET Porano		University of Bologna	
CNR IBBR Firenze	Centro BIODNA at Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore	CNR IRET Firenze		FEM - Ecologica Forestale	
CNR IRET Porano	Fondazione Edmund Mach - Ecologica Forestale	CNR IBBR Firenze		FEM-CRI	
University of Torino (DISAFA- Logo di Dipartimento di Scienze Agrarie, Forestali e Alimentari)	Fondazione Edmund Mach - Centro Ricerca e Innovazione (FEM-CRI)	ISPRA (Animali, Fungi)		CNR IRET Firenze	
Università degli studi di Napoli Federico II		FEM - Ecologica Forestale		CNR IRET Porano	

IZSLT (Istituto Zooprofilattico Sperimentale del Lazio e Toscana)		Centro BIODNA at Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore		CNR IBBR Firenze	
		CREA (Council for Agricultural Research and Economics)		Centro BIODNA at Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore	

The following organisations were identified as missing from the workshop:

- People from the ‘livestock world’: breeders’ associations
- People from the ‘wild world’: stakeholders from natural and protected areas (notably, the marine environment was not represented among the attending stakeholders)
- Experts on entomology, ornithology, and marine environments
- Ministry representatives
- Istituti Zooprofilattici Sperimentali IZS, (Experimental Zooprophyllactic Institutes)
- Researchers working in other ecosystems (e.g., the marine environment, which is highly relevant in Italy)
- Conservation practitioners
- CBD focal points
- Ministry of the Environment
- Representatives of the National Biodiversity Future Center
- People involved in reporting to the habitat and Bird Directives

Summary of current situation in Italy

One of the outcomes for the workshop was to create a common understanding of what the current situation concerning reporting to the CBD is. Therefore we asked a set of questions at the workshop to get an idea of how far Italy has come with monitoring and calculating genetic indicators.

Species list:

- No species list yet, but there are species with data on effective population size.
- No holistic vision for Italy from the ministry, but the scientific community was identified to be influential in shaping the vision.
- No methodology was put in place yet to create a species list.
- The Ministry of Environment needs to sign off a potential species list.

Data is collected and stored:

- Italy has the expertise to calculate effective population size (N_e) from DNA-based data.
- Some datasets exist

- For forests there is a database with 300 GCUs (Genetic Conservation Units) of 24 European tree species.
- Datasets on long-term population trends (spread across various institutions) for example in larger carnivores, beavers and bats exist, but the use of proxy data (non-DNA based data) is new.
- National forest inventory
- Fine scale remote sensing data to count trees, in order to establish a monitoring scheme in the future.

Reporting to the CBD:

- ISPRA is responsible for reports to the Red List.
- It is unclear how the reporting to the CBD should be conducted.

Challenges

The workflow for reporting to CBD was divided into three parts, and for each part, the workshop participants identified a list of challenges facing the stakeholders and the country to have a fully functional workflow that is repeatable for consecutive reporting cycles for the CBD.

After identifying the challenges, the participants reviewed them all and selected those for which they felt that developing solutions may benefit from collaboration with GINAMO (in other words, from co-creating solutions); versus those challenges that clearly need to be solved in-country. It was possible to mark a challenge as both a co-creation candidate and as a challenge that needs national work to be solved - but that is not indicated in this report. The challenges marked with (G) are the ones that were suggested for co-creation.

Species list to monitor and report on

- 1) Deciding which criteria to use for selecting **wild species**
 - Which criteria to use (e.g., conservation status ecosystem role, data availability, taxonomic representativeness, potential role in monitoring network)? (G)
 - Should key species or species representative of an ecosystem be prioritized? (G)
 - Should species be picked, which can act as indicator species? (G)
 - How to choose between endemic taxa, trans-boundary species (which are common in a neighbouring country) and species with available data on population trends? (G)
 - Which criteria for identifying the groups of interest and for assigning the role of model species within the group of interest? (G)
 - How to assess sampling feasibility vs. conservation relevance? (G)
- 2) Deciding which criteria to use for selecting **domestic species** (G)
 - How to include species of agricultural interest (e.g., traditional livestock, honey bees)?
 - Could economical impact be used to select crop species?

- 3) Collaborating with other countries for some common species (e.g., transboundary species) (G)
- 4) Get clarity on WHO has the mandate to do what (who has the mandate to lead/coordinate making the species list, often different ministries are in charge of different organisms)
- 5) Identify and unify scientific community for better political impact = 1 voice (to avoid bias in species selection)

Data is collected, structured and stored and calculating the indicators

- 1) Standardized way to calculate N_e of wild vs. domestic species/variety
 - things to check and consider with livestock species: is the sampling strategy ok? Account for management strategies, effect of crossbreeding on N_e estimates
- 2) What is the best method to calculate N_e depending on what DNA data you have? (G)
 - Which marker type?
 - Genetic or genomic data?
 - Should we consider the same marker type for every species?
- 3) How do we determine population boundaries? (G)
 - Do we have data on the entire species/all populations or just part of a population?
- 4) How to compare values coming from different DATA and different APPROACHES? (G)
- 5) Long-term monitoring data series might have gaps (e.g., due to the COVID pandemic), how do we treat those? (G)
- 6) What is a species? Which definition to use to define a species?
- 7) Satellite data is very large scale, but is it useful for individual species?
 - Scale issue? Fine-scale are promising as proxies to calculate genetic indicators, do we need multiscale/multi-sensor research data?
- 8) How to deal with clonal populations/species? (G)
- 9) There is a need for a standardized protocol for processing different data (e.g., reproducible, availability of data)
- 10) There is a need for methodology to translate proxies into N_c estimates
- 11) Concerns with indicators based on proxy data: (G)
 - What is the uncertainty with the N_e 500 indicator and how can we quantify it?
 - There is a risk of providing wrong or confusing indicator values based on proxy data. How can we prevent this?
 - There are no previous studies on the correlation between genetic diversity and proxy-based indicators. How reliable are they?

The report to the CBD is written and submitted

1. There should be a standard way for what CBD wants and how such reporting should look like
 - There was already a suggestion of creating maps of local populations with their associated genetic indicators, making it easily understandable for environmental managers and informative for the 'population maintained' indicator.

2. Should reporting the genetic indicators be a separate system or should it be integrated in other schemes?
3. Who takes the lead and manages this process for the whole country?

Next steps

The GINAMO work packages will assess all challenges selected by the five countries as potentially benefiting from collaboration between GINAMO and the country stakeholders. The GINAMO work package members will assess if and how these can be incorporated into their work, and how the country stakeholders might be able to contribute. The result of this will then be reported back to the country workshop participants, together with potential next steps.

Reference materials

- Belgium has committed to the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework and must report to the CBD using novel genetic indicators for the first time, among a large range of indicators, first in February 2026, and then periodically, typically every three to four years. Critical steps are the selection of species to report on, collecting and interpreting available data on them for the calculation of indicators, and using a reproducible approach to building successive reports. Guidelines for these steps are available:
 - CBD guidelines:
<https://www.cbd.int/doc/c/92cf/b458/18519b4c0b487bf9bfc23988/sbstta-26-inf-14-en.pdf>
 - Guidelines from the Coalition of Conservation Genetics:
<https://ccgenetics.github.io/guidelines-genetic-diversity-indicators/>
 - <https://doi.org/10.17161/bi.v18i.22332>
- Genetic diversity must be protected because it allows for the long-term persistence, resilience and adaptive potential of species.
 - policy brief: <https://g-bikegenetics.eu/en/multimedia-policy-briefs-pubs/policy-briefs>
- The genetic indicators are pragmatic and can be computed using DNA data or non-DNA proxy data.
 - <https://doi.org/10.1093/biosci/biae006>
 - <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10592-024-01632-8>
- These indicators have been tested and validated for use in 9 countries.
 - <https://doi.org/10.32942/X2WK6T>
- National Biodiversity Strategies and Action Plans (NBSAPs) can be improved to include the protection of genetic diversity.
 - <https://doi.org/10.1093/biosci/biae106>

APPENDIX I: Workshop Agenda

AGENDA - Belgium

09.00	Welcome / Introduction / Survey1	12.30	LUNCH
09.40	Presentation on GINAMO and genetic indicators	13.30	CS/C: Data extraction and calculation of indicators
10.15	BREAK	14.30	CS/C : reporting to Convention on Biological Diversity (CDB))
10.30	Workshop process/ reporting workflow	15.15	PAUSE
10.45	Participant introductions / organisational involvement	15.30	Sorting of challenges
11.15	Current Situation and Challenges (CS/C): species list	16.15	Next steps/Closure/Survey2
		17.00	THE END

Photo: Kristin Leus, GINAMO

APPENDIX II: institutions represented

Universities across Italy

Università Bologna

Università degli studi di Napoli Federico II

Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore

Università di Torino - DISAFA (Foreste e Legno)

Fondazione Edmund Mach

The Fondazione Edmund Mach (FEM) is a prominent Italian institution dedicated to research, education, and innovation in the fields of agriculture, food, and the environment. Present at the workshop were representatives from the Research and Innovation Centre (CRI) and the Unit Ecologica Forestale which is part of the CRI.

Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche (CNR)

CNR is Italy's largest public research institution, operating under the Ministry of University and Research. Present at the workshop were representatives from the Istituto di Bioscienza e Biorisorse (IBBR) which focuses on biological diversity, genetic resources, and biotechnologies for sustainable development; and the Istituto di Ricerca sugli Ecosistemi Terrestri (IRET) which focuses on terrestrial ecosystems, biodiversity, and the impacts of environmental changes such as pollution, climate change, and land use.

Parco nazionale delle Foreste Casentinesi

The Parco Nazionale delle Foreste Casentinesi is a national park in central Italy, spanning the regions of Tuscany and Emilia-Romagna.

ISPRA (Istituto Superiore Ricerca Ambiente)

ISPRA is a public research institute responsible for environmental protection and scientific research. It operates under the Ministry of Environment and Energy Security, focusing on monitoring, analyzing, and managing environmental risks, biodiversity, climate change, and sustainable resource use. ISPRA also coordinates the National System for Environmental Protection (SNPA), providing scientific data and policy recommendations to support environmental governance in Italy.

IZSLT (Istituto Zooprofilattico Sperimentale del Lazio e Toscana)

IZSLT is a public health institute in Italy specializing in veterinary research, food safety, and animal health. It operates under the supervision of the Ministry of Health and provides diagnostic, research, and surveillance services to monitor and prevent zoonotic diseases, ensure food safety, and support animal welfare in the Lazio and Tuscany regions.

APPENDIX III: IUCN SSC CPSG

Our **mission**: to save threatened species by increasing the effectiveness of conservation efforts worldwide

Our **mantra**: every species that needs a plan is covered by an effective and implemented plan

For over 40 years we've accomplished this by:

- Providing culturally sensitive and respectful facilitation for stakeholder-inclusive conservation action planning.
- Developing and sharing innovative, interdisciplinary science-based tools and methods.
- Building capacity for species conservation planning worldwide.